

28-10-2020

Deliverable D3.1

Tender Publication (OJEU notice)

Deliverable D3.1

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Document ID:	OCRE-20-355B8A
Authors:	Dave Heyns (GÉANT)

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Abstract

This document provides details on the publication of the OCRE cloud services (IaaS+) tender. The actual OJEU notice is referenced together with excerpts from the tender documents supporting the suppliers in terms of process.

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Executive Summary

The Open Clouds for Research Environments project (OCRE), aims to accelerate cloud adoption in the European research community, by bringing together cloud providers, Earth observation (EO) organisations and the research and education community, through ready-to-use service agreements and €9.5 million in adoption funding. Key to this are the tenders that will be published by OCRE.

The initial priority is to make commercial cloud and digital services available to the broader European research community with the intention to drive agility across research related tasks and activities and improve research outcomes. This will be achieved by means of a procurement framework providing easy access for researchers to a set of compliant, flexible digital tools by means of appropriate frameworks. This toolset will comprise of commodity cloud services (IaaS) with some related platform and software solutions.

A critical structural element of the cloud services procurement framework was examined by the EC review panel. After extensive market analysis and supplier engagement, the procurement team decided that the only way to ensure sustainable access to cloud-related digital services was to have suppliers of these services with a supportive local presence focused on the researcher at point of consumption. The only viable solution identified was to select suppliers (often resellers of cloud platforms with local servicing capabilities) via a lot per country. It is imperative that this design is understood and supported.

Once the cloud tender documents were approved by the Commission, the tender was published on the Negometrix platform and announced on TED on 16 April 2020 [[TED](#)]. The tender is scheduled to close on 23 June 2020 after which supplier bids will be evaluated and scored.

1 Introduction

This deliverable summarises OCRE's tender publication to the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU), where EU legislation requires all tenders from the public sector to be published that are valued above a certain financial threshold.

All documents related to this procedure are available to download via the eProcurement Portal [[Documents](#)]. The document “Information for Bidders” is Volume 0 of a set of 4 (0 to 3) comprising the tender documents relating to Stage 1 of this two-stage open procedure, and which includes the following volumes:

1. Volume 0 contains an overview of the procuring entities (GÉANT, the NREs and their member institutions) and the procurement process, guidance notes for bidders and general conditions.
2. Volume 1 is the “Guidance document to ESPD form” The actual ESPD form is only available on the Negometrix eProcurement portal [[Negometrix](#)].
3. Volume 2 is the “Invitation to Tender (ITT)”, which sets out the qualitative technical, operational, and commercial requirements.
4. Volume 3 is the “Framework Agreement” and the “Call-Off Agreement”, which contains the Terms and Conditions of Contract which will be used for contracting with supplier/s, subject to agreeing final terms and warranties.

GÉANT is using the open procedure under the Dutch Public Procurement Act (Aanbestedingswet 2012, revised 1 July 2016). Bidders are deemed to understand the processes that GÉANT is following under those regulations, and all applicable European Legislation and case law. Bidders participate in the process and submit detailed offers in the knowledge, and on the understanding and acceptance that these directives and rules apply to the end-to-end procurement process, and agree that these directives and rules apply unequivocally and that they will demonstrate adherence to them. By participating in this procurement, bidders are deemed to understand and comply with the procedures and conditions set out within this Volume 0, and as clarified in the other Volumes of the tender documents, as amended.

Table 1.1 provides an overview of the dates in this Open Procedure procurement process. GÉANT reserves the right to change these dates as necessary, although they will seek to minimise any changes.

Tender actions	Days	Start	Finish
Publish OJEU notice & ITT (Open Procedure) incl. contract terms	0	10 April 2020	
Period that questions can be send in	28	10 April 2020	20 May 2020
GÉANT will answers questions continuously. Final notice released		22 May 2020	
Bidder response time	43	10 April 2020	2 June 2020 – 12:00 CET
Deadline for sending in Offers		2 June 2020 – 12:00 CET	
Evaluate submitted Offers		2 June 2020	Mid-September
Intent to Award Contract(s) sent out & Debrief failed bidders via correspondence		End-June	End-October
Standstill period		20 days	
Contract production and finalization		July 2020	November 2020
Start Date Framework Agreements		July/August 2020	31 December 2020

Table 1.1: Procurement plan

The OJEU tender publication notice comprises three documents (the contract notice and two corrections) that are included in Appendix A, Appendix B and Appendix C of this deliverable. The documents are also available online on the TED website [[Notice](#)].

2 Conclusion

It is the intention that the conclusion of this procurement process will result in a number of Framework Agreements for IaaS+ solutions awarded to bidders who pass the Call for Competition evaluation, resulting in a portfolio of services for the customers to consume. The Frameworks will provide standardised contract terms for use by the research and education community. This will remove, or at least significantly reduce, the local overhead for technical, commercial or legal activities typically required when engaging new suppliers. As a result, this procurement will significantly reduce the barriers for the customers to consume IaaS+ solutions.

Framework Agreements are awarded to bidders (who are selected in accordance with the mechanisms described within this Call for Competition) for up to four years from the signing of the contract. It is expected that the Framework Agreements will be signed and become operational in Q4 2020. The Framework Agreements will have a contract term of 48 months, and will, therefore, be valid until Q4 2024. The term of each Call-Off Contract shall be as agreed between the parties to the Call-Off Contract but shall not in any event exceed four years.

The OCRE project team will communicate the portfolio of services resulting from the procurement initiative to the customers via various channels (including the NRENs and known research collaborations), and will work with bidders who secure a Framework Agreement on an ongoing basis to facilitate service adoption.

Appendix A Contract Notice

This notice in TED website: <https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:176523-2020:TEXT:EN:HTML>

II Netherlands-Amsterdam: IT services: consulting, software development, Internet and support 2020/S 074-176523

Contract notice Services

Legal Basis:

Directive 2014/24/EU

Section I: Contracting authority

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: GEANT Vereniging

National registration number: KvK 40535155 Postal

address: Hoekenrode 3

Town: Amsterdam NUTS

code: NL329

Postal code: 1102 BR Country:

Netherlands

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org

IV Internet address(es):

Main address: www.geant.org

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: RASH -Academic Network of Albania Town: Tirana

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Albania

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

V Internet address(es):

Main address: <https://www.rash.al/>

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: ASNET-AM Town:

Yerevan

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Armenia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org

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VI Internet address(es):Main address: www.asnet.am**I.1) Name and addresses** Official

name: ACOnet Town: Vienna

NUTS code: AT13 Country:

Austria

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org**VII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.aco.net**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: Belnet Town:

Brussels

NUTS code: BE10 Country:

Belgium

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org**VIII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.belnet.be**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: BREN Town: Sofia

NUTS code: BG412

Country: Bulgaria

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**IX Internet address(es):**Main address: www.bren.bg**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: CARNET Town:

Zagreb

NUTS code: HR041

Country: Croatia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**X Internet address(es):**Main address: www.carnet.hr**I.1) Name and addresses** Official

name: CYPNET Town: Nicosia

NUTS code: CY000

Country: Cyprus

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XI Internet address(es):**Main address: www.cynet.ac.cy**I.1) Name and addresses**

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<https://ted.europa.e>

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Official name: Cesnet

Town: Prague NUTS code:

CZ010

Country: Czechia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XII Internet address(es):

Main address: www.cesnet.cz

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: DeIC Town:

Lyngby

NUTS code: DK012

Country: Denmark

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XIII Internet address(es):

Main address: www.deic.dk

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: EENet Town: Tartu

NUTS code: EE008

Country: Estonia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XIV Internet address(es):

Main address: www.eenet.ee

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: CSC/FUNET Town:

Espoo

NUTS code: FI1B1

Country: Finland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XV Internet address(es):

Main address: www.csc.fi

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RENATER Town:

Paris

NUTS code: FR10 Country:

France

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XVI Internet address(es):

Main address: www.renater.fr

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: GRENA Town: Tbilisi

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Georgia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XVII Internet address(es):

Main address: www.grena.ge

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: DFN Town: Berlin

NUTS code: DE300

Country: Germany

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XVIII Internet address(es):

Main address: www.dfn.de

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: GRNET Town: Athens

NUTS code: EL30 Country:

Greece

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XIX Internet address(es):

Main address: www.grnet.gr

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: KIFU Town:

Budapest NUTS code: HU110

Country: Hungary

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XX Internet address(es):

Main address: www.niif.gov.hu

I.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RHnet Town:

Reykjavík NUTS code: IS001

Country: Iceland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

XXI Internet address(es):

Main address: www.rhnet.is

I.1) Name and addresses Official

name: HEAnet Town: Dublin

NUTS code: IE061

Country: Ireland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.heanet.ie**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: LUCC Town: Tel

Aviv

NUTS code: 00 Country: Israel

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXIII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.lucc.ac.il**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: GARR Town:

Roma

NUTS code: ITI43

Country: Italy

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXIV Internet address(es):**Main address: www.garr.it**I.1) Name and addresses** Official

name: LITNET Town: Kaunas

NUTS code: LT022

Country: Lithuania

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXV Internet address(es):**Main address: www.litnet.lt**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: RESTENA Town:

Esch sur Alzette NUTS code:

LU000 Country: Luxembourg

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXVI Internet address(es):**Main address: www.restena.lu

I.1) Name and addresses Official

name: MARnet Town: Skopje

NUTS code: 00

Country: North Macedonia Contact person:

Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXVII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.marnet.mk**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: University of Malta Town:

Msida

NUTS code: MT001

Country: Malta

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXVIII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.um.edu.mt**I.1) Name and addresses** Official

name: RENAM Town: Chisinau

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Moldova

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXIX Internet address(es):**Main address: www.renam.md**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: MREN Town:

Podgorica NUTS code: 00

Country: Montenegro

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXX Internet address(es):**Main address: www.mren.ac.me**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: SURF Town:

Utrecht

NUTS code: NL310

Country: Netherlands

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@gent.org **Internet****address(es):**Main address: www.surf.nl

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: UNIT Town:

Trondheim NUTS code: NO061

Country: Norway

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXI Internet address(es):**Main address: www.unit.no**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: PCSS Town:

Poznan

NUTS code: PL415

Country: Poland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.man.poznan.pl**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: FCT FCNN Town:

Lisbon

NUTS code: PT170

Country: Portugal

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXIII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.fccn.pt**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: RoEduNet Town:

Bucharest

NUTS code: RO321

Country: Romania

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXIV Internet address(es):**Main address: www.nren.ro**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: AMRES Town: Beograd

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Serbia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXV Internet address(es):**Main address: www.amres.ac.rs

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I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: ARNES Town:

Ljubljana NUTS code: SI031

Country: Slovenia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXVI Internet address(es):**Main address: www.arnes.si**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: RedIRIS/RED.ES Town:

Madrid

NUTS code: ES300

Country: Spain

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXVII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.rediris.es**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: SUNET Town:

Stockholm NUTS code: SE110

Country: Sweden

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXVIII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.sunet.se**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: SWITCH Town:

Zurich

NUTS code: CH040

Country: Switzerland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XXXIX Internet address(es):**Main address: www.switch.ch**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: ULAKBIM Town:

Ankara

NUTS code: TR51 Country:

Turkey

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XL Internet address(es):**Main address: www.ulakbim.tubitak.gov.tr

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I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: URAN Town: Kiev

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Ukraine

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XLI Internet address(es):**Main address: www.uran.ua**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: Jisc Town: Didcot

NUTS code: UKJ14

Country: United Kingdom Contact person:

Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XLII Internet address(es):**Main address: www.jisc.ac.uk**I.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: Institute of Ethnology and Social Anthropology, Slovak Academy of Sciences Town:

Brastlava

NUTS code: SK01 Country:

Slovakia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org**XLIII Internet address(es):**Main address: <https://www.sav.sk/>**I.2) Information about joint procurement**

The contract involves joint procurement

In the case of joint procurement involving different countries, state applicable national procurement law: See question 1.1.

The contract is awarded by a central purchasing body

I.3) CommunicationThe procurement documents are available for unrestricted and full direct access, free of charge, at: https://portal.negometrix.com/index.cfm?action=sourcing_requestform.subscribe&document=A4291E95-F50E-F0F5-EB8C8816F3C11AEA

Additional information can be obtained from the abovementioned address

Tenders or requests to participate must be submitted electronically via: https://portal.negometrix.com/index.cfm?action=sourcing_requestform.subscribe&document=A4291E95-F50E-F0F5-EB8C8816F3C11AEA**I.4) Type of the contracting authority**

Body governed by public law

I.5) Main activity

Other activity: Research and education networks

Section II: Object

II.1) Scope of the procurement**II.1.1) Title:**

Open Cloud for Research Environments (OCRE) — IaaS+ Cloud Tender 2020

II.1.2) Main CPV code

72000000

II.1.3) Type of contract

Services

II.1.4) Short description:

GÉANT is a not-for-profit organisation. The GÉANT Vereniging is owned by its core membership of 39 European National Research and Education Network (NREN) organisations and NORDUnet, which participates on behalf of five Nordic NRENS.

GÉANT executes this tender procedure on behalf of its members and may also act as a purchasing body on behalf of those members. The purpose of the procurement initiative is to bridge the demand and supply sides for Infrastructure-Platform- and Software as a Service (IaaS+). It is being conducted as an Open Procedure in accordance with the Dutch Public Procurement Act (Aanbestedingswet 2012, revised 1 July 2016).

The open procedure is divided in 40 lots. Each lot represents 1 Country. Per lot a number of frameworks can be awarded. The combined value of services over the lifespan of the frameworks agreements over all lots is estimated at EUR 600 000 000,-. Estimated value per lot vary be significantly. See document Vol 0. for more details.

II.1.5) Estimated total value

Value excluding VAT: 600 000 000.00 EUR

II.1.6) Information about lots

This contract is divided into lots: yes Tenders may be submitted for all lots

II.2) Description**II.2.1) Title:**

Albania

Lot No: 1

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS infrastructure as a service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: this definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer: PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary software services utilising bidders public IaaS/PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud 'marketplace') services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079.

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Armenia

Lot No: 2

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Austria

Lot No: 3

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: AT

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one

of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore is is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 50 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Belgium

Lot No: 4

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: BE

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The

consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 50 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Bulgaria

Lot No: 5

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: BG

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Croatia

Lot No: 6

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: HR

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 50 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Cyprus

Lot No: 7

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: CY

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating

systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Czech Republic Lot No: 8

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: CZ

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 25 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Denmark

Lot No: 9

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: DK

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 25 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Estonia

Lot No: 10

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: EE

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Finland

Lot No: 11

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: FI

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

France

Lot No: 12

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: FR

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 50 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Georgia

Lot No: 13

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Germany

Lot No: 14

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: DE

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Greece

Lot No: 15

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: EL

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Hungary

Lot No: 16

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: HU

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 25 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Iceland

Lot No: 17

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: IS

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Ireland

Lot No: 18

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: IE

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Israel

Lot No: 19

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Italy

Lot No: 20

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: IT

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Lithuania

Lot No: 21

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: LT

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Luxemburg

Lot No: 22

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: LU

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Macedonia

Lot No: 23

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Malta

Lot No: 24

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: MT

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Moldova

Lot No: 25

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Montenegro

Lot No: 26

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

The Netherlands Lot No:

27

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: NL

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 150 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Norway

Lot No: 28

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: NO

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Poland

Lot No: 29

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: PL

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 50 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Portugal

Lot No: 30

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: PT

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 25 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**XLIII.2) Description****XLIII.2.1) Title:**

Romania

Lot No: 31

XLIII.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

XLIII.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: RO

XLIII.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

XLIII.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

XLIII.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

XLIII.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Serbia

Lot No: 32

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Slovenia

Lot No: 33

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: SI

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Spain

Lot No: 34

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: ES

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

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This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

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Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Sweden

Lot No: 35

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: SE

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Switzerland

Lot No: 36

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: CH

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

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Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

Managed services or license based (e.g. VMs with applications pre-installed from a vendor's cloud "marketplace") services and general PaaS and SaaS services available in the marketplace and running in customer tenancies, may be included but these must be a direct consequence of the usage of IaaS services. One of the main objectives of the OCRE project is to create and further stimulate demand for IaaS+ services in Europe. For this specific objective the EC has made funds available that are to be distributed via the frameworks following this tender. Because of the current absence of demand for IaaS+ services in many Lots of this tender it is difficult to predict contract volumes over a period of 4 years, especially since the stimulation of demand in one of the main drivers behind this tender procedure. At the time of publication it is not known in which countries the EC adoption funds are to be spend.

Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 25 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Turkey

Lot No: 37

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: TR

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment. SaaS (Software as a Service)

Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

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Therefore it is hard to estimate the total spend for this Lot. The estimated spend is therefore an estimate only. No rights can be derived from the indicated estimated value.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

Ukraine

Lot No: 38

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: 00

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

Note: This definition of compute may include server and serverless computing for example virtual machines, FGPA's, etc.

This IaaS(+) solution or Solution may (optionally) also offer:

PaaS (Platform as a Service)

The capability provided to the consumer is to deploy onto the cloud infrastructure consumer-created or acquired applications created using programming languages, libraries, services, and tools supported by the provider. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

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Complementary Software services utilising Bidders Public IaaS / PaaS resources These complementary software service offerings must utilize (or be based on or directly related to) the Bidders Public IaaS resources (CPU, memory, storage, networking).

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II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information

II.2) Description

II.2.1) Title:

United Kingdom Lot No:

39

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: UK

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

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II.2.5) Award criteria

Price is not the only award criterion and all criteria are stated only in the procurement documents

II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 100 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues**II.2.13) Information about European Union funds**

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

This tender is part of the OCRE project. For more information see: <https://www.ocre-project.eu> The adoption funds are made available to the OCRE project by the European Commission under grant number 824079

II.2.14) Additional information**II.2) Description****II.2.1) Title:**

Slovakia

Lot No: 40

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

72000000

II.2.3) Place of performance

NUTS code: SK

II.2.4) Description of the procurement:

For this lot GEANT searches for providers who are able to offer and deliver the following solutions consisting of: IaaS Infrastructure as a Service

Where the consumer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, which can include operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications; and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls)

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II.2.6) Estimated value

Value excluding VAT: 5 000 000.00 EUR

II.2.7) Duration of the contract, framework agreement or dynamic purchasing system

Duration in months: 48

This contract is subject to renewal: no

II.2.10) Information about variants

Variants will be accepted: no

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.12) Information about electronic catalogues

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes Identification of the project:

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II.2.14) Additional information

Section III: Legal, economic, financial and technical information

III.1) Conditions for participation

III.1.1) Suitability to pursue the professional activity, including requirements relating to enrolment on professional or trade registers

III.1.2) Economic and financial standing

Selection criteria as stated in the procurement documents

III.1.3) Technical and professional ability

Selection criteria as stated in the procurement documents

III.1.5) Information about reserved contracts

III.2) Conditions related to the contract

n

III.2.1) Information about a particular profession**III.2.2) Contract performance conditions:****III.2.3) Information about staff responsible for the performance of the contract****Section IV: Procedure****IV.1) Description****IV.1.1) Type of procedure**

Open procedure

IV.1.3) Information about a framework agreement or a dynamic purchasing system

The procurement involves the establishment of a framework agreement

Framework agreement with several operators

Envisaged maximum number of participants to the framework agreement: 15

IV.1.4) Information about reduction of the number of solutions or tenders during negotiation or dialogue**IV.1.6) Information about electronic auction****IV.1.8) Information about the Government Procurement Agreement (GPA)**

The procurement is covered by the Government Procurement Agreement: no

IV.2) Administrative information**IV.2.1) Previous publication concerning this procedure**Notice number in the OJ S: [2019/S 149-367131](#)**IV.2.2) Time limit for receipt of tenders or requests to participate**

Date: 02/06/2020 Local

time: 12:00

IV.2.3) Estimated date of dispatch of invitations to tender or to participate to selected candidates**IV.2.4) Languages in which tenders or requests to participate may be submitted:**

English

IV.2.6) Minimum time frame during which the tenderer must maintain the tender

Duration in months: 6 (from the date stated for receipt of tender)

IV.2.7) Conditions for opening of tenders

Date: 02/06/2020 Local

time: 12:00 Place:

Amsterdam, the Netherlands

Information about authorised persons and opening procedure:

Tenders will be open in a digital environment. It is not possible to witness the opening to the received tenders.

Section VI: Complementary information**VI.1) Information about recurrence**

This is a recurrent procurement: no

VI.2) Information about electronic workflows

Electronic ordering will be used Electronic invoicing

will be accepted

VI.3) Additional information:**VI.4) Procedures for review**

VI.4.1) Review body

Official name: Rechtbank

Amsterdam Town:

Amsterdam

Country: Netherlands

Internet address: [https://www.rechtspraak.nl/Organisatie-en-contact/Organisatie/Rechtbanken/Rechtbank- Amsterdam](https://www.rechtspraak.nl/Organisatie-en-contact/Organisatie/Rechtbanken/Rechtbank-Amsterdam)

VI.4.2) Body responsible for mediation procedures**VI.4.3) Review procedure****VI.4.4) Service from which information about the review procedure may be obtained****VI.5) Date of dispatch of this notice:**

10/04/2020

Appendix B Additional Information: Correction 1

This notice in TED website: <https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:189244-2020:TEXT:EN:HTML>

3 Netherlands-Amsterdam: IT services: consulting, software development, Internet and support 2020/S 080-189244

Corrigendum

4 Notice for changes or additional information Services

(Supplement to the Official Journal of the European Union, 2020/S 074-176523)

5 Legal Basis:

Directive 2014/24/EU

Section I: Contracting authority/entity

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: GEANT Vereniging

National registration number: KvK 40535155 Postal address:

Hoekenrode 3

Town: Amsterdam NUTS

code: NL329

Postal code: 1102 BR Country:

Netherlands

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org

6 **Internet address(es):**

Main address: www.geant.org

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RASH - Academic Network of Albania Town: Tirana

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Albania

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

7 **Internet address(es):**

Main address: <https://www.rash.al/>

n

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: ASNET-AM Town:

Yerevan

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Armenia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org**8 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.asnet.am**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: ACOnet Town:

Vienna

NUTS code: AT13 Country:

Austria

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org**9 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.aco.net**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: Belnet Town:

Brussels

NUTS code: BE10 Country:

Belgium

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org**10 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.belnet.be**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: BREN Town: Sofia

NUTS code: BG412

Country: Bulgaria

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**11 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.bren.bg**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: CARNET Town:

Zagreb

NUTS code: HR041

Country: Croatia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**12 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.carnet.hr

n

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: CYNET Town:
Nicosia
NUTS code: CY000
Country: Cyprus
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

13 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.cynet.ac.cy

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Cesnet Town:
Prague
NUTS code: CZ010
Country: Czechia
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

14 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.cesnet.cz

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: DeiC Town:
Lyngby
NUTS code: DK012
Country: Denmark
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

15 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.deic.dk

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: EENet Town: Tartu
NUTS code: EE008
Country: Estonia
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

16 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.eenet.ee

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: CSC/FUNET Town:
Espoo
NUTS code: F11B1
Country: Finland
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

17 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.csc.fi

n

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: RENATER Town:

Paris

NUTS code: FR10 Country:

France

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**18 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.renater.fr**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: GRENA Town:

Tbilisi

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Georgia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**19 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.grena.ge**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: DFN Town: Berlin

NUTS code: DE300

Country: Germany

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**20 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.dfn.de**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: GRNET Town:

Athens

NUTS code: EL30 Country:

Greece

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**21 Internet address(es):**Main address: www.grnet.gr**1.1) Name and addresses**

Official name: KIFU Town:

Budapest NUTS code: HU110

Country: Hungary

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org**22 Internet address(es):**Main address: <https://kifu.gov.hu>**1.1) Name and addresses**

n

Official name: RHnet Town:
Reykjavfk NUTS code: 1S001
Country: Iceland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

23 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.rhnet.is

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: HEAnet Town:
Dublin
NUTS code: 1E061
Country: Ireland
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

24 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.heanet.ie

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: LUCC Town: Tel
Aviv
NUTS code: 00 Country:
Israel
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

25 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.lucc.ac.il

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: GARR Town:
Roma
NUTS code: 1T143
Country: Italy
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

26 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.garr.it

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: L1TNET Town:
Kaunas
NUTS code: LT022
Country: Lithuania
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

27 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.litnet.lt

1.1) Name and addresses

n

Official name: RESTENA Town:

Esch sur Alzette NUTS code:

LU000

Country: Luxembourg

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

28 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.restena.lu

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: MARnet Town:

Skopje

NUTS code: 00

Country: North Macedonia Contact person:

Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

29 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.marnet.mk

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: University of Malta Town:

Msida

NUTS code: MT001

Country: Malta

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

30 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.um.edu.mt

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: RENAM Town:

Chisinau

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Moldova

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

31 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.renam.md

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: MREN Town:

Podgorica NUTS code: 00

Country: Montenegro

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

32 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.mren.ac.me

1.1) Name and addresses

n

Official name: SURF Town:

Utrecht

NUTS code: NL310

Country: Netherlands

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@gent.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.surf.nl

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: UN1T Town:

Trondheim NUTS code: NO061

Country: Norway

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

33 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.unit.no

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: PCSS Town:

Poznan

NUTS code: PL415

Country: Poland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

34 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.man.poznan.pl

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: FCT FCNN Town:

Lisbon

NUTS code: PT170

Country: Portugal

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

35 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.fccn.pt

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RoEduNet Town:

Bucharest

NUTS code: RO321

Country: Romania

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

36 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.nren.ro

1.1) **Name and addresses**

n

Official name: AMRES

Town: Beograd NUTS

code: 00 Country: Serbia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

37 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.amres.ac.rs

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: ARNES Town:

Ljublijana NUTS code: S1031

Country: Slovenia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

38 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.arnes.si

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Red1R1S/RED.ES Town:

Madrid

NUTS code: ES300

Country: Spain

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

39 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.rediris.es

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: SUNET Town:

Stockholm NUTS code: SE110

Country: Sweden

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

40 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.sunet.se

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: SWITCH Town:

Zurich

NUTS code: CH040

Country: Switzerland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

41 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.switch.ch

1.1) Name and addresses

n

Official name: ULAKBİM Town:

Ankara

NUTS code: TR51 Country:

Turkey

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

42 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.ulakbim.tubitak.gov.tr

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: URAN Town: Kiev

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Ukraine

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

43 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.uran.ua

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Jisc Town: Didcot

NUTS code: UKJ14

Country: United Kingdom Contact person:

Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

44 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.jisc.ac.uk

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Institute of Ethnology and Social Anthropology, Slovak Academy of Sciences Town:

Bratislava

NUTS code: SK01 Country:

Slovakia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor

E-mail: Olaf.verschoor@geant.org

45 Internet address(es):

Main address: <https://www.sav.sk/>

Section II: Object

11.1) Scope of the procurement

11.1.1) Title:

Open Cloud for Research Environments (OCRE) – 1aaS+ Cloud Tender 2020

11.1.2) Main CPV code

72000000

11.1.3) Type of contract

Services

11.1.4) Short description:

GEANT is a not-for-profit organisation. The GEANT Vereniging is owned by its core membership of 39 European National Research and Education Network (NREN) organisations and NORDUnet, which participates on behalf of five Nordic NRENs.

GEANT executes this tender procedure on behalf of its members and may also act as a purchasing body on behalf of those members. The purpose of the procurement initiative is to bridge the demand and supply sides for Infrastructure- Platform- and Software as a Service (IaaS+). It is being conducted as an open procedure in accordance with the Dutch Public Procurement Act (Aanbestedingswet 2012, revised 1 July 2016).

The open procedure is divided in 40 lots. Each lot represents 1 country. per lot a number of frameworks can be awarded.

The combined value of services over the lifespan of the frameworks agreements over all lots is estimated at EUR 600 000 000. Estimated value per lot vary be significantly. See document Vol 0. for more details.

Section VI: Complementary information

V1.5) **Date of dispatch of this notice:**

21/04/2020

46 V1.6) **Original notice reference**

Notice number in the OJ S: [2020/S 074-176523](#)

Section VII: Changes

V11.1) **Information to be changed or added**

47 V11.1.2) **Text to be corrected in the original notice**

Section number: 1.1)

Lot No: 16

Place of text to be modified: Internet address(es) KIFU

Hungary Instead of:

Main address:

www.niif.gov.hu Read:

Main address:

<https://kifu.gov.hu>

V11.2) **Other**

additional

information:

Appendix c Additional Information: Correction 2

This notice in TED website: <https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:230240-2020:TEXT:EN:HTML>

48 Netherlands-Amsterdam: IT services: consulting, software development, Internet and support 2020/S 096-230240

Corrigendum

49 Notice for changes or additional information Services

(Supplement to the Official Journal of the European Union, 2020/S 074-176523)

50 Legal Basis:

Directive 2014/24/EU

51 Section I: Contracting authority/entity

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: GEANT Vereniging

National registration number: KvK 40535155 Postal address:
Hoekenrode 3

Town: Amsterdam NUTS

code: NL329

Postal code: 1102 BR Country:

Netherlands

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

Olaf.verschoor@geant.org Internet

address(es):

Main address: www.geant.org

1.1) Name and addresses

Official name: RASH - Academic Network of Albania Town: Tirana

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Albania

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org Internet

address(es):

Main address: <https://www.rash.al/>

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: ASNET-AM Town:

Yerevan

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Armenia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

Olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.asnet.am

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: ACOnet Town:

Vienna

NUTS code: AT13 Country:

Austria

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

Olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.aco.net

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: Belnet Town:

Brussels NUTS code: BE10

Country: Belgium

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

Olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.belnet.be

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: BREN Town: Sofia

NUTS code: BG412

Country: Bulgaria

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.bren.bg

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: CARNET Town:

Zagreb

NUTS code: HR041

Country: Croatia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.carnet.hr

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: CYNET Town:
Nicosia
NUTS code: CY000
Country: Cyprus
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org

52 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.cynet.ac.cy

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: Cesnet Town:
Prague
NUTS code: CZ010
Country: Czechia
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet
address(es):**

Main address: www.cesnet.cz

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: DeIC Town:
Lyngby
NUTS code: DK012
Country: Denmark
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet
address(es):**

Main address: www.deic.dk

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: EENet Town: Tartu
NUTS code: EE00 Country:
Estonia
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet
address(es):**

Main address: www.eenet.ee

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: CSC/FUNET Town:
Espoo
NUTS code: F11B1
Country: Finland
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet
address(es):**

Main address: www.csc.fi

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RENATER Town:

Paris
NUTS code: FR10 Country:
France
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor
E-mail: olaf.verschoor@geant.org

53 Internet address(es):

Main address: www.renater.fr

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: GRENA Town:
Tbilisi

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Georgia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.grena.ge

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: DFN Town: Berlin

NUTS code: DE300

Country: Germany

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.dfn.de

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: GRNET Town:

Athens

NUTS code: EL30 Country:

Greece

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.grnet.gr

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: KIFU Town:

Budapest NUTS code: HU110

Country: Hungary

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.niif.gov.hu

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RHnet Town:

Reykjavfk NUTS code: IS001

Country: Iceland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):

Main address: www.rhnet.is

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: HEAnet Town:

Dublin

NUTS code: 1E061

Country: Ireland

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):

Main address: www.heanet.ie

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: LUCC Town: Tel

Aviv

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Israel

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):

Main address: www.lucc.ac.il

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: GARR Town:

Roma

NUTS code: 1T143

Country: Italy

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):

Main address: www.garr.it

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: L1TNET Town:

Kaunas

NUTS code: LT022

Country: Lithuania

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):

Main address: www.litnet.lt

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RESTENA Town:

Esch sur Alzette NUTS code:

LU000

Country: Luxembourg
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):

Main address: www.restena.lu

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: MARnet Town:

Skopje

NUTS code: 00

Country: North Macedonia Contact person:

Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.marnet.mk

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: University of Malta Town:

Msida

NUTS code: MT001

Country: Malta

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.um.edu.mt

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RENAM Town:

Chisinau NUTS code: 00

Country: Moldova

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.renam.md

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: MREN Town:

Podgorica NUTS code: 00

Country: Montenegro

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.mren.ac.me

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: SURF Town:

Utrecht

NUTS code: NL310
Country: Netherlands
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@gent.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.surf.nl

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: UN1T Town:
Trondheim NUTS code: NO061
Country: Norway
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.unit.no

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: PCSS Town:
Poznan
NUTS code: PL415
Country: Poland
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.man.poznan.pl

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: FCT FCNN Town:
Lisbon
NUTS code: PT1 0 Country:
Portugal
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.fcn.pt

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: RoEduNet Town:
Bucharest
NUTS code: RO321
Country: Romania
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.nren.ro

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: AMRES

Town: Beograd NUTS
code: 00 Country: Serbia
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.amres.ac.rs

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: ARNES Town:
Ljubljana NUTS code: S1031
Country: Slovenia
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.arnes.si

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: Red1R1S/RED.ES Town:
Madrid
NUTS code: ES300
Country: Spain
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.rediris.es

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: SUNET Town:
Stockholm NUTS code: SE110
Country: Sweden
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.sunet.se

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: SWITCH Town:
Zurich
NUTS code: CH040
Country: Switzerland
Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:
olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**
address(es):
Main address: www.switch.ch

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: ULAKBİM Town:

Ankara

NUTS code: TR51 Country:

Turkey

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.ulakbim.tubitak.gov.tr

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: URAN Town: Kiev

NUTS code: 00 Country:

Ukraine

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.uran.ua

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: Jisc Town: Didcot

NUTS code: UKJ14

Country: United Kingdom Contact person:

Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: www.jisc.ac.uk

1.1) **Name and addresses**

Official name: Institute of Ethnology and Social Anthropology, Slovak Academy of Sciences Town:

Bratislava

NUTS code: SK01 Country:

Slovakia

Contact person: Olaf Verschoor E-mail:

Olaf.verschoor@geant.org **Internet**

address(es):

Main address: <https://www.sav.sk/>

54 **Section II: Object**

11.1) **Scope of the procurement**

11.1.1) **Title:**

Open Cloud for Research Environments (OCRE) — 1aaS+ Cloud Tender 2020

11.1.2) **Main CPV code**

2000000

11.1.3) **Type of contract**

Services

11.1.4) **Short description:**

GEANT is a not-for-profit organisation. The GEANT Vereniging is owned by its core membership of 39 European National Research and Education Network (NREN) organisations and NORDUnet, which participates on behalf of five Nordic NRENS.

GEANT executes this tender procedure on behalf of its members and may also act as a purchasing body on behalf of those members. The purpose of the procurement initiative is to bridge the demand and supply sides for Infrastructure – Platform – and software as a service (IaaS+). It is being conducted as an open procedure in accordance with the Dutch Public Procurement Act (Aanbestedingswet 2012, revised 1 July 2016).

The open procedure is divided in 40 lots. Each lot represents one Country. Per lot a number of frameworks can be awarded.

The combined value of services over the lifespan of the frameworks agreements over all lots is estimated at EUR 600 000 000. Estimated value per lot vary be significantly. See document Vol 0. for more details.

55 **Section VI: Complementary information**

V1.5) **Date of dispatch of this notice:**

14/05/2020

56 V1.6) **Original notice reference**

Notice number in the OJ S: [2020/S 0 4-1 6523](#)

57 **Section VII: Changes**

V11.1) **Information to be changed or added**

58 V11.1.2) **Text to be corrected in the original notice**

Section number: 1V.2.2)

Lot No: Change valid for all Lots. (Lot 1-Lot 40)

Place of text to be modified: Time limit for receipt of tenders or requests to participate – time limit extended Instead of:

Date:

02/06/

2020

Local

time:

12:00

Read:

Date:

23/06/

2020

Local

time:

12:00

V11.2) **Other additional information:**

Due to the ongoing Covid-19 situation in Europe GEANT has decided to extend the time limit for receipt of tender.

References

- [Documents]** <https://supply2.geant>
- [TED]** <https://ted.europa.eu/>
- [Negometrix]** Requires Negometrix login:
https://portal.negometrix.com/index.cfm?action=sourcing:requestform.questionnairereview&workspace_id=7cjl7&requestform_id=h4l3ew&element_id=ivdvyi
- [Notice]** <https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:176523-2020:TEXT:EN:HTML>

Glossary

ESPD	European Single Procurement Document
CET	Central European Time
EC	European Commission
EO	Earth observation
EU	European Union
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ITT	Invitation to Tender
NREN	National Research and Education Network
OCRE	Open Clouds for Research Environments
OJEU	Official Journal of the European Union